

SZ-HB-III-01-01 Search for other prospective Students (English)

Author	@Julia Victoria Dinier ; @Ricarda Peil ; @Julia Lehmler ; @Sönke Erdmann ; @Karin Elbrecht ; @Tara-Marie Endries ; @Alexander Schröter (original German version) @Jan Martin Kauter ; @Tara-Marie Endries ; @Emily Penk (English translation)
Doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091489
ID	SZ-HB-III-01-01
Title	Search for other prospective Students
Educational area	#school #higher-education
Persona	P: Carlotta - Without assignment https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14615153
Short description	Prospective student Carlotta is looking for other prospective students who are in a similar situation.
Result	Carlotta finds a prospective student XY to discuss a possible course of study and the challenges of everyday student life in retirement.
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem scenario• Activity scenario<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Part 1: "Search for contacts"• Part 2: "Prospective students match and exchange ideas"
Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Carlotta is registered at BIRD• Carlotta is logged in to BIRD• Prospective student is registered at BIRD• Prospective student is logged in to BIRD
Components	#data-wallet #buddyfinder #chat
Services / tools	#BIRD-Calendar #video-conference

Problem scenario

Introduction

After a long career, Carlotta Pocelli is now retired. She enjoys the free time she has gained and can now fully pursue her hobbies and interests. While she was employed, she had the dream of studying again, but she simply didn't have enough time. That's changed now, and she has decided to use her retirement to pursue a bachelor's degree in nutritional science.

Problem definition

Carlotta would like to exchange ideas with other people in a similar situation, whether they are other older freshmen or people who are making a fresh start in retirement. She would like to discuss the challenges of such a new beginning and share her concerns with others. Carlotta would be delighted to find someone who is in the same situation or even a little further along than she is.

Background and context

A second degree in a different field is always a challenge, but doing it all in retirement is a different story. Carlotta fears that her digital skills might not be sufficient and is looking for allies so they can exchange ideas and, if necessary, prepare together.

Impact of the problem (on the Persona)

Carlotta is a seasoned woman with many years of professional experience and expertise in the field of agricultural sciences. She has decided that she wants to learn more and delve deeper into her hobby of nutrition. It's not a lack of willingness to learn; she's just worried that she won't be able to pass her studies in today's digital age. She's concerned that such a small part as the digital component could have a major impact on her and her dream of studying nutritional science.

Pre BIRD attempts at a solution

Carlotta has already asked her friends if they know anyone who is facing the same challenge. However, she hasn't found anyone that way. She has also discussed this topic with her children, and through them, Carlotta realizes that a lot has changed and that she needs to further expand her digital expertise. She briefly considered giving online forums a chance and looking for support there, but dismissed the idea after a brief research.

Activity scenario

Part 1: "Search for contacts"

Step 1: Carlotta knows she wants to start studying again. Now that she's retired, she has plenty of time and wants to continue learning. However, she can't really assess the challenges this might entail. Therefore he would like to exchange ideas with someone in a similar situation.

Step 2: She visits BIRD and has read about the BuddyFinder a few times, and she's

curious to see if she can use this tool to find people in a similar situation.

Step 3: She didn't updated her BIRD profile for a while now, so she's checking to see if she needs to change any information or maybe even add new ones.

Step 4: After Carlotta has checked her information, she navigates to the BuddyFinder by clicking on the bird on the homepage. This seems to her to be the easiest way to access the tool.

Step 5: She's not completely sure how the BuddyFinder works yet, but she knows she'll figure it out. When the BuddyFinder opens, it asks if she wants to look for something or offer something.

Step 6: Carlotta clicks on "search" because she wants to find people to exchange ideas with.

Step 7: The Buddy Finder search opens and Carlotta can enter her information to be matched with one or more possible buddies. First she carefully reads everything and provides the following information:

- State: all
- City: all
- University/College: all
- graduation: university degree
- Semester: before starting / prospective student
- Interests: studying while retired, starting over
- Group or individual: individual

Step 8: The BuddyFinder generates an anonymized list of results based on the data entered.

Step 9: Carlotta looks at the results list and has to orientate herself to understand how the matching works.

Step 10: After a short time, she realizes that the results are ordered, and the most relevant matches are listed first. This helps her in her decision, as she would prefer to talk to someone who is also retired and ready to make a fresh start.

Step 11: Carlotta selects the buddy which matching her search criteria the most and sends a contact request for networking.

Step 2: "Prospective students match and exchange ideas"

Step 1: Carlotta receives a message that her contact request has been accepted and a shared chat pops up.

Step 2: Carlotta immediately writes a message in the chat to introduce herself to her buddy.

Step 3: Her buddy does the same and the two start talking and can share their questions and concerns.

Step 4: For Carlotta, it is easier to communicate by phone because she is not used to write on a computer keyboard and it is simply tiring for her. She asks her buddy if they want to schedule a video conference.

Step 5: They arrange an appointment for the following week and Carlotta enters it in her BIRD calendar so that she won't forget the meeting.